

ISic0016

I.Sicily inscription 0016

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo

Archeologico Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 3516

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1

: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2

: mm

Text

1. I, m, p(eratori) C, a[es(ari)L(ucio)] S(eptimio) · Sever[o]
2. P, i, o P[ertinaciA] u(usto) Arab(ico) · Adiabe[nico]
3. [Pa]r, t, h(ico) · [max(imo)pont(ifici)] max(imo) · tr(ibunicia) · pot(estate) · VI · imp(eratori)
4. X, I co(n)s(uli) · II · p(atrici) · p(atriciae) · pro[co](n)s(uli) · imp(eratoris) · Caes(aris) · divi
5. M(arci) · Antonini · Pii · G[e]rm(anici) Sarmatic[i] · f(ilio)
6. divi Commodi frat[er]i divi Antoni
7. ni Pii nepoti · divi · Hadriani prone
8. [p]oti divi · Traiani Parthici ab[n] [(epoti)]
9. [d]ivi · Nervae · adnepoti indulgen
10. [tis]simo et clementissimo principi
11. [dom]jino nostro · res p(ublica) · Panhorm(itanorum)
12. [Iiv]ir(orum) · P(ubli) Satyri Donati et M(arci) Maeci
13. [R]ufini d(ecreto) d(ecurionum)

Apparatus

Text of ILMusPalermo

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491776

EDR 137832

EDCS 22000860

Bibliography

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